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Dux family transcription factor activation during TNBC resistance.

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Dux family transcription factor activation occurred concomitant with PRDM13 activation. DUXAP9 and DUXAP10 induction supported the assertion that one mechanism by which cancer cells resist clinical intervention is by directly re-engaging machinery that ultimately results in activation of transformation.